

Inter-EURLs Working Group on NGS (NEXT GENERATION SEQUENCING)

Foreword

The WG has been established by the European Commission with the aim to promote the use of NGS across the EURLs' networks, build NGS capacity within the EU and ensure liaison with the work of the EURLs and the work of EFSA and ECDC on the NGS mandate sent by the Commission. The WG includes all the EURLs operating in the field of the microbiological contamination of food and feed and this document represents a deliverable of the WG and is meant to be diffused to all the respective networks of NRLs.

Guidelines for amplicon sequencing of the capsid region of noroviruses

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1. Introduction

In this document, methodologies for amplicon sequencing of the capsid region of human noroviruses (from now on, referred as norovirus) are described. The document comprises guidance for the wet laboratory work (i.e. RNA-extraction, reverse transcription, PCRs and sequencing) as well as sequence analysis and determination of genotypes (bioinformatics). These guidelines convey all steps generally required for implementation of next generation sequencing based norovirus typing and have been drafted to assist novices to implement NGS in their typing strategy. In addition, specific and complete method descriptions are appended to these general guidelines.

For subtyping of norovirus the capsid-region is the most commonly used region and a nomenclature of genogroups and genotypes has been developed (Chhabra et al, 2019). Of all noroviruses, genogroups I, II and IV primarily affect humans. Norovirus genogroup I and II are causative of the majority of the disease burden worldwide. A region of about 300 bp is usually amplified using PCR and then sequenced. Traditionally, such sequencing was performed by Sanger sequencing but the use of Next Generation Sequencing (NGS) enables typing of several genotypes within the same sample (Ollivier et al, 2022). This is important for environmentally contaminated foods or waters that might contain more than one genotype. Due to genomic heterogeneity, typing of noroviruses is generally performed separately for each genogroup.

It is also possible to also sequence the polymerase region (PoI) of norovirus to further increase typing resolution. However, this is out of scope for the current version of this document.

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2. Overview of the amplicon-seq workflow

The method for norovirus capsid metabarcoding analysis consists of several stages: RNA extraction, reverse transcription (RT), first round PCR (referred below as PCR) and second round, semi-nested PCR (referred to as N-PCR), sequencing and bioinformatic analysis and genotyping. An overview of the method is given in figure 1.

Random primers can be used for reverse transcription. Random hexamers, nonamers or a mixture of hexamers and nonamers have also been applied for this purpose.

RNA complementary DNA molecules (cDNA) are amplified during two rounds of PCR. A nested PCR approach is employed for enhanced sensitivity, avoiding spurious DNA amplification that would arise from excessive single-round PCR. Potentially, RT and PCR can be combined into a single reaction, although this has not been extensively tested for all relevant sample types.

The DNA must be prepared for NGS-sequencing and this process is called library construction. To this end, all DNA must be adapted to accommodate a sequencing adaptor on both ends of the fragment. A sequencing adaptor is commonly composed of multiple functional regions, including a segment to bind to the sequencing flow cell and a barcode that is used to distinguish multiple libraries that are sequenced simultaneously. For cost-effective multiplexed deep sequencing, sequencing adaptors can be incorporated using a PCR strategy. Alternatively, a more labour-intensive blunt-ending and adaptor ligation strategy could be employed.

After N-PCR amplification, cDNA mixes can be analysed using gel electrophoresis. 1% agarose gel is suitable to identify the presence of norovirus capsid amplicons. Alternatively, a capillary electrophoresis instrument could be employed. Accurate DNA library quantification is essential for pooling of libraries before sequencing. This can be done using fluorometry, barcode PCR or capillary electrophoresis.

Users should be aware of some limitations inherent to amplicon sequencing, such as primer bias which means different genotypes are not amplified with the same efficiency.

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Figure 1. Overview of the amplicon sequencing of Norovirus workflow

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3. RNA extraction

To reduce the effect of RT-PCR inhibitors, the use of an RNA extraction method that yields high purity RNA is crucial. The extraction of RNA from samples is preferably performed according to the ISO-standard 15216-1:2017: "Microbiology of the food chain - Horizontal method for determination of hepatitis A virus and norovirus using real-time RT-PCR - Part 1: Method for quantification".

Certain matrices can still cause inhibition of the PCRs and an extra clean-up step might therefore be necessary. One such kit is the OneStep™ PCR Inhibitor Removal Kit (Zymo Research). Quantifying the amount of RNA in the eluate can be difficult if the concentration is low and the use of digital PCR might then be a suitable approach. For high-concentration samples a fluorometric assay such as the Qubit Fluorometer or NanoDrop spectrophotometer (Thermo Fisher Scientific) system would suffice.

4. PCR amplification

Amplicon sequencing of RNA sequences relies on RT-PCR to convert RNA into cDNA for subsequent amplification and sequencing. However, the initial RT step can be performed using two strategies: one-step and two-step RT-PCR. Each approach offers advantages and disadvantages, influencing your choice based on your specific needs. Apart from the sample, negative matrix and water controls should also be added.

4.1 Two-step RT-PCR

4.1.1 RT

In the RT-reaction, the RNA is transcribed to complementary DNA (cDNA) by the reverse transcriptase enzyme. The reaction can be performed either using specific primers that anneal to a specific locus, which is then transcribed, or by using non-specific random hexamers and/or nonamers. The resulting cDNA can be used as a template in the following step: the first PCR.

4.1.2 First PCR

In the first PCR, the cDNA is synthesized in the RT-step is amplified by using primers specific to the typing region to be analysed. The PCR-reactions for GI and GII are performed separately.

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4.2 One-step RT-PCR

The one-step approach combines both RT and PCR in a single reaction, streamlining workflow and reducing processing time. It also minimises sample handling, lowering the risks of introducing unwanted amplicons. It is possible to use either the specific reverse primer or random hexa- and nanomers as RNA primers for the generation of cDNA. Relying on the specific primers to generate cDNA could miss some new types of sequences but at the same time the PCR would not amplify the region and cause a two-step to fail. As the one-step enzyme mix is a compromise between the preferred buffers of the RNA and DNA polymerase this alternative could be less sensitive. However, in some cases the one-step master mix can analyse a greater volume of the extracted sample than the two-step that dilutes the sample in each step.

4.3 Second/Semi-nested PCR

To be able to sequence DNA on an Illumina machine, the DNA needs to be fragmented and adaptor sequences must be added at the ends of the prepared DNA-fragments. These adaptors anneal to complementary sequences on the Illumina flow cell. Therefore the primers of the second PCR-step are usually appended with overhang adapter sequences for compatibility with Illumina index and sequencing adapter. This creates specific amplicons across the region of interest with adapter sequences at the beginning and end of the amplicon that enables the amplicon to be processed further into a sequencing library.

4.4 QC of PCR-products

Before continuing with the library preparation, a QC step may be performed to ensure that products are present and to be able to adjust the DNA amount used in the following step. Confirmation of products can be performed by either an agarose gel analysis or by using a Bioanalyzer 2100 (Agilent) or similar technique. Quantification is preferably performed using the Qubit system, Nanodrop or similar system.

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5. Sequencing libraries and Illumina sequencing

5.1 Create libraries

To create sequencing libraries (i.e. DNA fragments with attached adapters) adapter sequences must be added to the ends of each DNA-fragment. The adapter sequences contain three parts; 1) the index sequences for multiplexing 2) the sequences used for annealing the fragments to the flow cell surface 3) and the PCR-primer binding sites used in sequencing. If the above-mentioned PCR-primer modification (4.3) was used, the amplicon should now have sequences at the ends that enable the amplicons to be further processed by a library preparation kit. A suitable kit would be the NexteraXT Library Preparation Kit (Illumina) where the initial tagmentation steps are omitted. Start the protocol from the post-PCR wash using AMPure XP beads. Following the wash the index PCR is performed to incorporate indexes unique to each sample. These primers can only be used if the primers in the nested PCR were modified with the appropriate Illumina adapter sequence. The final step is again a post-PCR wash. The amplicons should now be PCR-amplified DNA-amplicons extended with the Illumina adapters. See figure 2 below for an illustration of the library preparation step.

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Figure 2. Library preparation workflow. The combination of different Index 1 and 2 enables pooling of all the libraries into one run and the resulting sequence reads are demultiplexed and put into the corresponding files automatically by the sequencer. The P5 and P7 adaptors are complementary to DNA strands attached on the flow cell surface. From: https://support.illumina.com/documents/documentation/chemistry_documentation/16s/16s-metagenomic-library-prep-guide-15044223-b.pdf

5.2 QC of libraries

The quality and quantity of the sequencing libraries can be determined (roughly) by the Bioanalyzer 2100 (Agilent) or similar equipment. The Bioanalyzer 2100 is an electrophoresis apparatus that can

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analyse up to 11 samples on one chip/run. The purpose of this QC-step is to ensure that the libraries form a peak at around the expected fragment size (i.e., the amplicon length plus the adapter sequence length). The quantity of each library is needed if the libraries are manually normalised for concentration before the pooling step below. Included in the NexteraXT-kit are normalising beads that can perform the normalisation of each library and if those are used, only the concentration of the final pool of libraries should be measured. Otherwise, each library must be measured and diluted manually to a common concentration for all libraries. Since the size of a successfully prepared library is known by design, the Bioanalyzer step can be replaced using a fluorometric assay that measures the concentration with higher accuracy. The Qubit fluorometer (Thermo Fisher) is an example of an apparatus that measures concentration of DNA in a sample. When the amount of DNA and the average size of the library is known the molarity of the library can be calculated by the following formula:

$$\frac{(\text{concentration in ng}/\mu\text{l})}{(660 \text{ g/mol} * \text{average library size in bp})} * 10^6 = \text{concentration in nM}$$

5.3 Kit selection and library pooling

Before the actual sequencing is performed, a suitable reagent kit size must be selected.

There are different reagent kits for the Illumina machines. This guide focuses on the MiSeq instrument since it is widely used and has a suitable amount of output. There are, however, both larger and smaller machines available which might be suitable for amplicon sequencing as well. However, only the NextSeq 1000 and NextSeq 2000 Systems can offer the read lengths that the MiSeq can produce. As there is much experience of the MiSeq for this application, these guidelines will focus on that instrument.

There are large reagent kits (version 3-kits) that produce up to 25 million sequence reads per run. This means that if 25 samples are analysed in one run, they can each yield a million reads and this extreme amount of data is unnecessary. Presumably it would be enough with the order of thousands of reads per sample but that would require very small kits and a high level of multiplexing (i.e., many samples in one run) to reach that low. To keep costs down, the MiSeq Reagent Nano Kit v2 is a suitable kit to start with. This reagent kit produces up to 2,000,000 paired-end reads and its small size is suitable when setting up a new method. The read length is 250 bp in each direction which covers most typing regions. However, to fully cover both the Pol and the Cap region of Norovirus, this read length is too short.

The number of samples that can be analysed in one run can be determined by dividing the maximum number of reads produced by a kit with the number of reads wanted per sample. This calculation

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assumes that all samples are perfectly normalised and sequenced and this is never the case. Some samples will produce more reads than others so it is recommended to aim for a higher coverage than needed. Since the MiSeq reagent kits are designed to sequence several whole bacterial genomes or small eukaryotes in one run, the output is usually several-fold higher than what is needed to determine the genotype from for instance the Cap-region. This means that it is probably the number of indexes available that will limit the number of samples that can be sequenced in one run, even when using the smaller kits.

PhiX Control library is a concentrated library created from a small bacteriophage (PhiX174) genome that can be purchased from Illumina. The library has an average size of 500 bp and a GC-content of 45%. It is used as calibration control, run quality monitoring and also as a colour balancer. In whole genome sequencing it is commonly added in a small amount to the sample pool for run-quality monitoring. However, when performing amplicon sequencing most, if not all, fragments being sequenced have the exact same sequence. This means that for a certain cycle in the run, there might be identical signals from all clusters or almost none which makes it difficult for the software to call high quality bases and positions. Adding the PhiX adds diversity and balances fluorescence signals at each cycle to improve the overall run quality. For amplicon sequencing it is not uncommon to add up to 40% of PhiX to a run.

The actual pooling consists of adding certain amounts of each sample library to a new tube to ensure all libraries are represented equally in the pool. The pool is then denatured according to the instructions of the manufacturer and loaded on the MiSeq Reagent Cartridge for sequencing.

The loading concentration to the sequencing instrument is important. Loading too much library can lead to over-clustering of the flow cell which yields low quality data or no data at all. In addition, as the PCR-amplicons have a low diversity this problem could be even greater. Illumina recommends loading concentrations that differs between the version of flow cell used:

For MiSeq

- MiSeq Reagent Kit v3: This kit supports a loading concentration range of 6-20 pM.
- MiSeq Reagent Kit v2: This kit has a narrower recommended loading concentration range of 6-10 pM.

Although with an amplicon-based method you should start testing within the lower region of the concentration range.

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5.4 Quality control of run parameters

After the sequencing is complete, certain quality parameters should be inspected after the run as a quality control step of the sequencing run.

The parameters include:

- 1) **Cluster density.** This is a metric that can influence the run quality, how many reads that pass the filter, quality values and the amount of data produced in a run. A cluster is a spot on the flow cell that represents one single fragment from the library meaning one cluster leads to one sequence read. If the clusters are too densely packed the software cannot separate them which means that the Q-values (i.e., quality value per base) will be lowered. It can also lead to clusters not passing the filter which means they cannot be separated by the base-calling software and this leads to a lower total output of usable data.
If instead the cluster density is low, the quality of the reads is often high but the total number of output reads will be low. The goal is to sequence at high enough densities to yield a large data output but not so high that overclustering effects appear. The optimal clustering density varies between both machines and kits.
- 2) **%Passed Filter or %PF** is a measure of the percentage of clusters passing filter and is an indication of signal purity from each cluster. Overclustered flow cells typically have higher numbers of overlapping clusters. This leads to poor template generation, which then causes a decrease in the %PF metric. It is difficult to recommend a certain number that is acceptable. If the amount of data is enough for the downstream analysis and the Q-values (see below) are high there might not be a problem with a low %PF.
- 3) **Q30%** is a measure of the percentage of bases that are of quality value Q30 or above. The Q-values are logarithmic and a Q10-base has a 1/10 error rate. A sequence read of Q10-bases could have one erroneous base for each ten in the sequence. Q20 means that 1/100 bases is possibly wrong and Q30 therefore means that 1/1000 bases is wrong. The value is usually dependent on the clustering value. If the run is overclustered the Q-values usually decrease. Since Q30 basically means that the whole read is accurate, Q30 and above is the quality of reads that should be aimed for and is commonly used as a quality parameter.
- 4) **PhiX.** In the Sequencing Analysis Viewer (SAV) software on the Illumina-machine the amount of PhiX-reads that have been successfully aligned to the reference sequence can be found. The percentage of aligned reads should be roughly about the same percentage added to the sample

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pool before sequencing. However, the main purpose of PhiX is to add diversity and if you get enough good data from all sequenced samples, this QC-step might not be necessary.

- 5) **Reads distribution per sample.** The distribution of reads is visible in several places during the post-sequencing analysis. If the reads are copied from the machine to a bioinformatics computer, the file sizes are visible and the file sizes are a good relative measurement of the number of reads each sample represents. It will also become apparent when the bioinformatics analysis starts. However, it is recommended to look at the run in the Sequencing Analysis Viewer (SAV) on the Illumina-machine before the analysis starts. The distribution of reads and all the quality metrics mentioned above are visible there with more in-depth detail than from the control software used to sequence the samples.

6. Bioinformatics analysis

The bioinformatics analysis comprises all the steps needed to get from the raw sequence reads to an end result (identification of all genotypes of Norovirus in the sample). When such a complex analysis involves several steps and several different scripts/programs, connected in series, to perform the complete analysis, the use of pipelines is recommended. A pipeline performs several or all steps of an analysis and minimises hands-on time and the risk of human errors. Some available pipelines and workflows will be discussed at the end of this section but all the individual steps are first discussed below along with examples of software.

6.1 Quality control of reads

To evaluate the quality of the sequence reads, the vast amount of quality data needs to be summarised. A software that performs this is FastQC which is a java-application that can be downloaded from <https://www.bioinformatics.babraham.ac.uk/projects/fastqc/>. The software summarises several different quality parameters but the perhaps most relevant one is the “Per base sequence quality” which shows how the qualities vary on average across the sequence length (see figure 3). If the sequence quality drops severely towards the end a quality trimming step is needed to trim away the low-quality bases at the end of the sequences. After trimming, FastQC can be run again to see the effect of the trimming.

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Figure 3, showing the per base sequence quality values in FastQC from a sample (not amplicon) sequenced on a MiSeq. The non-linear x-axis is the base position in the reads and the y-axis is the Q-score. The green area represents high quality, the yellow area represents reasonable quality and the red area represents poor quality values which should be trimmed from the reads. The blue line is the average quality values across all reads.

FastQC can also show adapter contamination and adapters should be trimmed away before further analysis (see figure 4).

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Figure 4, showing adapter contamination in a sample in FastQC. The red line shows the % of adapter sequence in the total number of reads at certain read positions. It is clear that starting around base 90 the % of reads containing adapter sequence increases. Note that this is an example of a run where the method needs optimising, usually the adapter contamination is very low and probably not visible in such a plot.

FastQC will report an error on library diversity when performing amplicon sequencing but this is expected. See figure 5 below for an example.

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Well-balanced

Low diversity

Figure 5. Upper figure showing the Percent Base plot displayed by Illumina Sequencing Analysis Viewer (SAV) for a sequenced norovirus capsid amplicon NGS library. Lower figure showing the Percent Base plot in SAV for a well-balanced library compared to a low diversity library (figure from Illumina). Although a well-balanced NGS library is preferred, amplicon NGS libraries will always look like a low diversity NGS library in the SAV Percent Base plot.

When a pipeline has been set up or adapted to the workflow, there is perhaps no need to visually inspect the quality values for each run. The low-quality bases and the adaptors are taken care of in the trimming stages described below. However, if the analysis shows poor results, it can be valuable to use FastQC to help troubleshoot.

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6.2 Adapter and primer trimming

The sequence adapters described in 5.1 can sometimes be sequenced by the sequencer if the fragments (the amplicons) are too short. The majority of them are removed by the sequencer but since removing all of the adapters is crucial before further analysis, a separate adapter trimming step is recommended.

One software that performs this step is Trimmomatic

<http://www.usadellab.org/cms/?page=trimmomatic>

Trimmomatic can remove adapters from any sequencer by specifying the sequence of the adapters. The adapter sequences for most sequencers are provided with the software but the start command must still contain the file path to the fasta-file with the adapter sequences. Trimmomatic can also trim low-quality bases at the same time (see 6.3).

The instrument usually removes the Illumina-specific sequences of each read but the primer sequence used in the second PCR-amplification would still be there. It is important to remove these so they do not impact the typing.

In the Geneious software this can be done using the “Trim ends” function, either searching for the primer sequences and remove them or trimming a specific number of nucleotides corresponding to the length of the primers from the 5' end.

The software FROGS (see. 6.8.1) has a preprocessing tool that trim primer sequences.

6.3 Quality trimming

Quality trimming is extremely important for amplicon metagenomic reads so that minor differences in sequences caused by PCR and sequencing errors are not mistaken for real variation. One of the most widely used quality trimming software is Trimmomatic. It can remove adapters, trim low-quality bases from both directions and use different methods to determine when to trim bases.

Another, newer software that performs both the quality control and the trimming/filtering is fastp (<https://github.com/OpenGene/fastp>). It is a faster solution than Trimmomatic even though it performs quality control, adapter trimming, quality filtering and per-read quality trimming. It can also auto-detect which adaptors are in the dataset and remove them. It also has functionality to remove sequences of low variability, e.g., reads with much repetition or long stretches of the same nucleotide.

In the Geneious software a simple way of trimming the sequences is to use the BBDuk Adapter and quality trimming tool. As we have a lot of reads and should have sufficient data of high quality, a quality score of Q30 is recommended. At the same time, it is possible to remove short reads that is not interesting for the analysis. The tool is also able to remove the Illumina specific adapters if for some reason they would still be there.

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6.4 Merging paired reads

Illumina sequencers read the DNA-fragment from both ends which yields two reads. If the fragment is short enough and the read length long enough, the reads will overlap. The two reads can then be merged into one continuous read. The quality of reads is lowest at the end and when the forward read and reverse read are merged, it is the ends that overlap and this can elevate the quality of the overlapping region.

Tools like FLASH, fastp and BBMerge (Geneious) use algorithms to align and merge overlapping regions, considering quality scores and trimming low-quality bases. To produce correct merges the tools may require optimisation of parameters such as “minimal overlap length” and “mismatch tolerance”. After merging it is possible that some sequences are much shorter or longer than the expected products of your PCR region. The longer sequences may either be contaminations or incorrectly merged sequences, so those should be removed. Short sequences do not contain enough sequence to be correctly classified and should also be removed. For this size selection a tool that separates the sequences of a defined size range similar to the expected product with some margin, for example ± 10 bp. This can be done with a size selection tool in Geneious prime or the standardize length function of the FROGS pipeline.

Merging overlapping regions is prone to creating chimeric sequences, i.e., artificial fusions of different molecules, so be sure to use tools with chimera detection features like FLASH or a separate chimera detection step as described below. Merging the reads is an **optional** step in the workflow.

6.5 Chimera removal

Chimeras arise when two or more genuine DNA fragments get incorrectly joined during library preparation or amplification steps. This can happen primarily due to:

PCR mispriming: Similar sequences from different molecules anneal and get amplified, creating hybrids.

Template switching: During amplification, polymerase switches from one nucleotide strand to another to continue synthesis, generating fused products.

Chimeric reads can interfere with results because they may resemble novel genes or mutations, leading to erroneous interpretations. That can lead to an inflated diversity of genotypes and they should be identified and removed before the typing step below. The two main approaches to remove chimeras are the database and *de novo* approaches.

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The database approach uses pre-existing databases of sequences identified as chimeras in previous studies, known artefacts or features indicative of chimerism and reference genomes from different organisms to detect interspecies chimeras.

The approach is fast but is reliant on the chimeras already being present in the database

The *de novo* approach instead relies on computational algorithms to analyse the data intrinsically and identify chimeric sequences without prior knowledge. It is computationally more intensive and might require careful parameter tuning to avoid misidentifying genuine sequences as chimeras.

Software that performs these tasks are e.g., VSEARCH and UCHIME (used in Geneious). The FROGS pipeline also has a chimera removal step.

6.6 Clustering of reads

In amplicon sequencing experiments, the sequencers yield millions of short sequencing reads.

However, not all reads represent unique information and it is not practically feasible to genotype them one by one.

Some reads may represent:

Sequencing errors: Introduced during the sequencing process itself.

PCR duplicates: Identical copies generated during amplification steps.

Chimeras: Artificial fusions of DNA fragments from different molecules.

Clustering helps address these issues by grouping very similar reads together. This serves two crucial purposes:

1. Reduces redundancy:

Eliminates PCR duplicates and sequencing errors, reducing noise and improving data quality.

Increases computational efficiency by analysing representative sequences instead of millions of individual reads.

2. Defines Operational Taxonomic Units (OTUs) or Amplicon Sequence Variants (ASVs):

Clusters represent unique "molecular units" within the samples.

Each cluster defines an OTU (species-level) or ASV (single DNA molecule variant) for downstream analysis.

Clustering helps interpret diversity and community composition but might not always reflect true biological diversity due to limitations in distinguishing close variants.

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There are several clustering methods, but broadly they fall into two categories:

1. Distance-based clustering:

Each read is compared to all others using a "distance metric".

Reads within a predefined distance threshold are grouped into clusters.

Common tools include USEARCH and VSEARCH.

2. Swarm-based clustering:

Reads are initially assigned to "seed" sequences and then other reads compete to join clusters based on similarity to seed sequences. The cluster membership evolves iteratively until a stable state is reached.

Example software includes DADA2 and Deblur.

There is also a third way that might be easier to use which is assembly-based clustering.

This is done by performing a *de novo* assembly with very high-stringency settings to cluster all similar sequences into separate contigs. Each contig will represent a cluster consensus sequence and represent an OTU. The method in appendix B utilizes this method.

The choice of clustering method and distance threshold depends on the question and data characteristics. Regardless of method an optimisation of, for instance, the threshold value, might be needed as overly stringent thresholds can merge real variants, while lenient thresholds might group unrelated sequences.

6.7 Filtering of results

From the clustering of reads, a number of identified clusters is given as output and some of these clusters represent a large part of the total number of reads and some clusters only represent a few reads. According to the EFSA report (Ollivier J. et al.) norovirus reads are always present in low levels in the negative controls as well and this might be due to mis-sequencing of the index sequences for instance. That is why it is recommended to apply an identification threshold to exclude clusters that represent less than a certain percentage of the total number of reads.

Another way of performing this step is to use a threshold value for each run based on the levels in the negative matrix control. The use of thresholds might not be necessary for patient samples where one genotype is expected to be found in high levels. But for a food sample that might contain several different genotypes it may be required to accurately interpret the final results.

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6.8 Pipelines

6.8.1 FROGS

A pipeline that can perform the above-mentioned steps is FROGS which analyses large sets of amplicon sequences and from those, create abundance tables of OTUs or ASVs. It can be run within a Galaxy-instance (<https://galaxyproject.org/>) meaning that the user can control the workflow via a graphical user interface. It is also possible to run via the terminal command line which means that the pipeline is configured and started by writing commands. Accessing the software via a terminal requires Linux or WSL2 in Windows (which enables the use of Linux from within Windows). Both methods do require a higher level of computer-knowledge to get the software installed and configured.

The different tools of the pipeline can be run independently or as a workflow. It was not designed for norovirus but for amplicons in general. Assigning genotypes to ASVs is not possible directly within the pipeline but by submitting sequences of ASVs to the Norovirus Typing Tool V2.0 (<https://www.rivm.nl/mpf/typingtool/norovirus/>). Another way to assign taxonomy to ASVs is to set up a norovirus database formatted for the FROGS pipeline. Tutorials on the command line (high level of bioinformatics/computer knowledge needed) can be found in the Migale portal (<https://migale.inrae.fr/>).

FROGS has a homepage (<https://frogs.toulouse.inrae.fr/>) that contains links to the software, a user manual and other relevant information.

6.8.2 Geneious Prime and other commercial software

The software Geneious Prime contains different types of software described above and they can be run in sequence in a graphical user interface. Geneious Prime is not a so-called open-source software that FROGS is which means there is a licensing cost to use the software. However, the level of bioinformatics/computer knowledge needed to get going is much lower and this therefore represents a more beginner-friendly option. There are other commercial software available but Geneious Prime is one of the more affordable. The company producing Geneious has a tutorial on how to run amplicon metagenomics using their software: (<https://www.geneious.com/tutorials/metagenomic-analysis/>). These commercial bioinformatics software can also perform a wide variety of other operations on sequencing data and can therefore be used for more than just amplicon sequencing analysis.

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6.8.3 In-house pipeline

The term in-house pipeline refers to a pipeline that has been built by staff at the institute where it will be used. This approach offers a pipeline that is purpose-built for the methods and lab routines in place. It can also be optimised better to the actual laboratory method instead of adapted from another application intended for a similar analysis (e.g., a pipeline for bacterial 16S can be modified to capsid typing).

Some aspects of building your own pipeline are that it:

- requires a programmer/bioinformatician - both to build it but also to maintain it
- requires thorough testing and validation
- gives you better control of what the pipeline does and can be adapted to future method changes.

6.9 Typing

The final step in the bioinformatics analysis is the actual determination of the genotypes in the sample. From the steps and pipelines described above, the result is a list of clusters and perhaps each clusters' abundance. The final typing step can be performed either by querying a local database of norovirus sequences or by uploading the sequences to an online database. The latter might be preferred as the online databases contain the most up-to-date sequences and the current nomenclature for the genotypes. There are at least two databases that performs the typing:

1. Norovirus Typing Tool www.rivm.nl/mpf/typingtool/norovirus/
2. Human calicivirus typing tool <https://calicivirustypingtool.cdc.gov/>

Both tools accept one or more sequences in FASTA-format, either pasted into a text box directly on the webpage or uploaded as a file by browsing your computer. The FASTA format is a sequence text format that starts with a ">" symbol followed by a name/descriptive text on the same row. From the second row and up to the next ">" or the end of the file, the sequence follows and can be in one single line or multiple lines (which is preferred for long sequences).

Example of a multi-FASTA file with 2 sequences:

```
>Cap-sequence 1, oyster sample X
ATCGCGAGCTTACGGCACATTTTCGAA
TTTAGGACGCGGCCCTTCAACATGGT
>Cap-sequence 2, faecal sample Y
ATCGCGAGCTTACGGCACATTTTCGAA
```

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TTTAGGACGCGGCCCTTCAACATGGT

Up to 20,000 sequences can be uploaded at the same time for the Norovirus Typing Tool. Results for multiple sequences are presented in table form.

Bibliography

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Ollivier J, Lowther J, Desdouits M, Schaeffer J, Wacrenier C, Oude Munnink BB, Besnard A, Mota Batista F, Stapleton T, Schultz AC, Aarestrup F, Koopmans M, de Graaf M and Le Guyader S, 2022. Application of Next Generation Sequencing on Norovirus-contaminated oyster samples. EFSA supporting publication 2022:EN-7348. 125 pp. doi:10.2903/sp.efsa.2022.EN-7348

Frédéric Escudié, Lucas Auer, Maria Bernard, Mahendra Mariadassou, Laurent Cauquil, Katia Vidal, Sarah Maman, Guillermina Hernandez-Raquet, Sylvie Combes, Géraldine Pascal, FROGS: Find, Rapidly, OTUs with Galaxy Solution, *Bioinformatics*, Volume 34, Issue 8, April 2018, Pages 1287–1294, <https://doi.org/10.1093/bioinformatics/btx791>

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Appendix A – Method 1 (EFSA)

1. Scope

The present document describes the protocol of amplification of norovirus by RT- (N) PCR for classical typing and metabarcoding approach applied to nucleic acid extracts as described in the ISO 15216-1 and 15216-2 protocols.

2. Reference documents

- Ollivier J., Lowther J., Desdouits M., Schaeffer J., Wacrenier C., Oude Munnink B. B., Besnard A., Mota Batista F., Stapleton T., Schultz A.C., Aarestrup F., Koopmans M., de Graaf M., Le Guyader F.S. 2022. Application of next generation sequencing on norovirus-contaminated oyster samples. *EFSA Supporting Publications*, 19(6), DOI: 10.2903/sp.efsa.2022.EN-7348
- Kojima S., Kageyama T., Fukushi S., Hoshino F.B., Shinohara M., Uchida K., Natori K., Takeda N., Katayama K. 2002. [Genogroup-specific PCR primers for detection of Norwalk-like viruses](#). *J. Virol. Methods* 100: 107-14; DOI: 10.1016/s0166-0934(01)00404-9
- Le Guyader F., Neill F.H., Estes M.K., Monroe S.S., Ando T., Atmar R.L. 1996. [Detection and analysis of a small round-structured virus strain in oysters implicated in an outbreak of acute gastroenteritis](#). *Appl Environ Microbiol.* 62 : 4268-72; DOI: 10.1128/aem.62.11.4268-4272.1996
- Loisy F., Le Cann P., Pommepuy M., Le Guyader F. 2000. An improved method for the detection of Norwalk-like caliciviruses in environmental samples. *Lett. Appl. Microbiol.* 31 (6) : 411-5; DOI: 10.1046/j.1365-2672.2000.00837.x
- Yuen L.K., Catton M.G., Cox B.J., Wright P.J., Marshall J.A. 2001. [Heminested multiplex reverse transcription-PCR for detection and differentiation of Norwalk-like virus genogroups 1 and 2 in fecal samples](#). *J. Clin. Microbiol.* 39: 2690-4; DOI: 10.1128/JCM.39.7.2690-2694.2001

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3. Precautions

Handle all reagents for preparation of reaction mix in a separate, clean environment to avoid contamination. Wear a lab coat and disposable gloves when handling.

3.1. Equipment, environment or consumables

- Freezer > -15°C
- Fridge 5°C±3°C
- Hood
- Pipettes (de 1µL à 1000µL)
- Benchtop centrifuge
- Vortex
- Multipette stream dispenser, Eppendorf and sterile 1mL combitips
- Filter tips, sterile (10µL, 100µL, 200µL, 1000µL)
- Tubes type Eppendorf 0.6 mL, 1.5 mL and 2 mL
- Lab coat
- Gloves

3.2. Reagents

- Random hexamers (Invitrogen, Cat N° N8080127)
- Random nonamers (Sigma, Cat N° R7647)
- Primers – 10 µM working solutions
- SuperScript IV (Invitrogen, Cat N° 18090050)
- RNase OUT (Invitrogen Cat N° 10777-019)
- Platinum Taq Polymerase (Invitrogen, Cat N° 10966-026)
- dNTP
- Molecular biology grade water

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PCR	Direction	Name	Primer sequence	Reference
Norovirus GI				
PCR	F	QNIF4	CGCTGGATGCGNTTCCAT	Loisy et al., 2000
	R	GISKR	CCAACCCARCCATTRTACA	Kojima et al., 2002
N-PCR	F	GISKF_NGS	TCGTCGGCAGCGTCAGATGTGTATAAGAGACAGCTGCCGAATTYGTAAATGA	Kojima et al., 2002
	R	GISKR_NGS	GTCTCGTGGGCTCGGAGATGTGTATAAGAGACAGCCAACCCARCCATTRTACA	Kojima et al., 2002
Norovirus GII				
PCR	F	QNIF2D	ATGTTCAgRTGGATGAGRTTCTCWGA	Loisy et al., 2000
	R	GIISKR	CCRCCNGCATRHCCRTTRTACAT	Kojima et al., 2002
N-PCR	F	GIISKF_NGS	TCGTCGGCAGCGTCAGATGTGTATAAGAGACAGCNTGGGAGGGCGATCGCAA	Kojima et al., 2002
	R	GIISKR_NGS	GTCTCGTGGGCTCGGAGATGTGTATAAGAGACAGCCRCCNGCATRHCCRTTRT ACAT	Kojima et al., 2002

Note: for metabarcoding application, the primers used during the Nested-PCR should bear a tag allowing the addition of barcodes in a following round of PCR (10 cycles, done by sequencing platform). Illumina overhang sequences used in present protocol (**Illumina overhang**-locus-specific sequence)

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4. Procedure

Check that the reagents are thawed. All reagents must be carefully homogenized before use.

To avoid contaminations, handle all products in a separate, clean environment away from nucleic acid extracts.

4.1. RT

Prepare the mixes as described in the following tables for one sample, adapt quantities to the number of reactions needed.

Composition of mixes based on the SuperScript IV kit:

In A tube mix:

Reagents	Initial concentration	Volume/reaction (µl)
H ₂ O	-	3
Random hexamers	50µM	1
Random nonamers	50µM	1
RNA template	-	7

In B tube mix:

Reagents	Initial concentration	Volume/reaction (µl)
First-Stand Buffer	5X	4
DTT	0,1 M	1
dNTP	10 µM	1
RNaseOUT	40 units/µL	1
SuperScript II	200 units/µL	1

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Place the tubes with mix A in thermocycler and incubate:

5 minutes at 65°C

- Transfer tubes on ice for 3-4 min.
- Add 8 µL of mix B: final reaction volume = 20 µL
- Put tubes A+B in thermocycler and start the program:
 - 10 minutes at 25°C
 - 50 minutes at 42°C
 - 15 minutes at 70°C
- Take out tubes and directly proceed to PCR or store the cDNA at 4°C for a few days, at temperature ≤ -20°C for up to 6 months and at temperature ≤ -70°C for longer storage.

4.2. PCR

- Prepare the reaction mix, based on Taq Platinum kit (Invitrogen):

Reagents	Initial concentration	Volume/reaction (µl)
H ₂ O	-	30,3
PCR Buffer, without Mg	10X	5
dNTP	10 mM	1
MgCl ₂	50 mM	1,5
PCR primer Fwd	10 µM	1
PCR primer Rev	10 µM	1
Platinum Taq DNA polymerase	20 U/µl	0,2

Distribute 40 µL of PCR mix in PCR tubes and add 10 µL of cDNA.

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- Place the tubes in thermocycler and start the program:

95°C 1 minute

40 cycles of:

- 95°C 30 seconds
- 50°C 30 seconds
- 72°C 30 seconds

Final elongation at 72°C for 7 minutes

- Take out the tubes and store at 4°C or proceed to Nested PCR.
- Store the amplicons at 4°C for a few days, at temperature ≤ -20°C for up to 6 months and at temperature ≤ -70°C for longer storage.

4.3. Nested PCR

Prepare the reaction mix, based on Taq Platinum kit (Invitrogen):

Reagents	Initial concentration	Volume/reaction (µl)
H ₂ O	-	38,3
10X PCR Buffer, without Mg	10X	5
dNTP	10 mM	1
MgCl ₂	50 mM	1,5
NPCR primer Fwd (primer with Illumina overhangs)	10 µM	1
PCR primer Rev (primer with Illumina overhangs)	10 µM	1
Platinum Taq DNA polymerase	5 U/µl	0,2

Distribute 48 µL of PCR mix in PCR tubes and add 2 µL of PCR product.

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Note: According to PCR results, it is possible to add up to 5 µL of PCR product (in this case adjust the volume of water).

- Place the tubes in thermocycler and start the program:

95°C - 1 minute

40 cycles of:

- 95°C - 30 seconds
- 50°C - 30 seconds
- 72°C - 30 seconds

Final elongation at 72°C for 7 minutes

- Take out the tubes and store at 4°C for a few days, at temperature ≤ -20°C for up to 6 months and at temperature ≤ -70°C for longer storage.

4.4. Gel electrophoresis

Verify the amplification efficiency by electrophoresis in 1% of agarose gel. The amplicon sizes are as follows:

Virus	Amplification	Primers (F – Rev)	Amplicon size (bp)
GI	PCR	QNIF4 – GISKR	380
	N-PCR	GISKF_NGS – GISKR_NGS	396
GII	PCR	QNIF2D - GIISKR	378
	N-PCR	GIISKF_NGS - GIISKR_NGS	410

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4.5 Bioinformatics analysis using FROGS pipeline

Several tutorials are available to help you get started with the FROGS pipeline via the Galaxy portal:

https://usegalaxy.org/pages/list_published

<https://frogs.toulouse.inra.fr/html/tuto.html>

The bioinformatic processing is done using a workflow of processing steps in a predetermined order:

Step 1: Upload FASTQ files

The raw sequencing run data must be transferred to a network drive that has backup enabled. The FASTQ files from the run are then uploaded to the Galaxy portal from the folder.

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Step 2: Quality check

Use the FastQ-C tool to check the quality of the sequencing.

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FastQC Report

Summary

- Basic Statistics
- Per base sequence quality
- Per tile sequence quality
- Per sequence quality scores
- Per base sequence content
- Per sequence GC content
- Per base N content
- Sequence Length Distribution
- Sequence Duplication Levels
- Overrepresented sequences
- Adapter Content

Per base sequence quality

Degraded sequencing quality should be considered when setting up the Pre-process step, by reducing the Mismatch rate

Step 3: FROGS Pre-Process

In the Pre-Process step of the pipeline, fill in the fields with the parameters corresponding to the amplicons to be analysed. For each sample, please provide the following:

- Sample name, corresponding file the path for R1&R2 fastq file
- Read size, depending of the specification of the sequencing run
- Expected amplicon size
- Mismatch rate
- Minimum amplicon size
- Maximum amplicon size
- 5' primer
- 3' primer

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FRIGS Pre-process merging, denoising and dereplication (Galaxy Version 4.0.1-galaxy1)

Sequencer
Illumina

Select the sequencing technology used to produce the sequences.

Input type
Files by samples

Samples files can be provided in a single TAR archive or sample by sample (both one or two files each).

Are reads already merged?
No

The inputs contain 1 file by sample - R1 and R2 pair are already merged in one sequence.

Samples
1: Samples

Name
3-4

The sample name.

Reads 1
20 TSS1-3-C-GI+dbp_S144_U001_R2_001.fastq.gz (as fastq.gz)

R1 FASTQ file of paired-end reads.

Reads 2
20 TSS1-3-C-GI+dbp_S144_U001_R2_001.fastq.gz (as fastq.gz)

R2 FASTQ file of paired-end reads.

Insert Samples

Reads 1 size
The maximum read1 size.

Reads 2 size
The maximum read2 size.

Mismatch rate
0.1

The maximum rate of mismatches in the overlap region.

Merge software
Vsearch

Select the software to merge paired-end reads (-merge-software)

History
TSS1-GI rdmp
790.39 MB

62: MultiQC on data 60, data 58, and others: Webpage	ⓧ	✕
61: MultiQC on data 60, data 58, and others: Stats a list with 3 items		
60: FastQC on data 20: RawData	ⓧ	✕
59: FastQC on data 20: Webpage	ⓧ	✕
58: FastQC on data 19: RawData	ⓧ	✕
57: FastQC on data 19: Webpage	ⓧ	✕
56: FastQC on data 18: RawData	ⓧ	✕
55: FastQC on data 18: Webpage	ⓧ	✕
54: FastQC on data 17: RawData	ⓧ	✕
53: FastQC on data 17: Webpage	ⓧ	✕
52: FastQC on data 16: RawData	ⓧ	✕
51: FastQC on data 16: Webpage	ⓧ	✕
50: FastQC on data 15: RawData	ⓧ	✕
49: FastQC on data 15: Webpage	ⓧ	✕
48: FastQC on data 14: RawData	ⓧ	✕
47: FastQC on data 14: Webpage	ⓧ	✕
46: FastQC on data 13: RawData	ⓧ	✕
45: FastQC on data 13: Webpage	ⓧ	✕
44: FastQC on data 12: RawData	ⓧ	✕
43: FastQC on data 12: Webpage	ⓧ	✕
42: FastQC on data 11: RawData	ⓧ	✕
41: FastQC on data 11: Webpage	ⓧ	✕

FRIGS

Reads 1 size
300

The maximum read1 size.

Reads 2 size
300

The maximum read2 size.

Mismatch rate
0.1

The maximum rate of mismatches in the overlap region.

Merge software
Flash

Select the software to merge paired-end reads (-merge-software)

Expected amplicon size
323

Maximum amplicon length expected in approximately 90% of the amplicons (-expected-amplicon-size)

Would you like to keep unmerged reads?
No

Yes: Unmerged reads will be excluded; Yes: unmerged reads will be artificially combined with 100 N. (default No) (-keep-unmerged)

Minimum amplicon size
300

The minimum size for the amplicons (with primers) (-min-amplicon-size)

Maximum amplicon size
400

The maximum size for the amplicons (with primers) (-max-amplicon-size)

Sequencing protocol
Illumina standard

The protocol used for sequencing (step: standard or custom with PCR primers as sequencing primers).

5' primer
GATCGGATTCACAGCGTGGG

The 5' primer sequence (boldcards are accepted). The orientation is detailed below in 'Primers parameters' help section (-five-prim-primer)

3' primer
TAGCGGATGATGATGATG

The 3' primer sequence (boldcards are accepted). The orientation is detailed below in 'Primers parameters' help section (-three-prim-primer)

Email notification
No

Send an email notification when the job completes.

Execute

History
TSS1-GI rdmp
790.39 MB

62: MultiQC on data 60, data 58, and others: Webpage	ⓧ	✕
61: MultiQC on data 60, data 58, and others: Stats a list with 3 items		
60: FastQC on data 20: RawData	ⓧ	✕
59: FastQC on data 20: Webpage	ⓧ	✕
58: FastQC on data 19: RawData	ⓧ	✕
57: FastQC on data 19: Webpage	ⓧ	✕
56: FastQC on data 18: RawData	ⓧ	✕
55: FastQC on data 18: Webpage	ⓧ	✕
54: FastQC on data 17: RawData	ⓧ	✕
53: FastQC on data 17: Webpage	ⓧ	✕
52: FastQC on data 16: RawData	ⓧ	✕
51: FastQC on data 16: Webpage	ⓧ	✕
50: FastQC on data 15: RawData	ⓧ	✕
49: FastQC on data 15: Webpage	ⓧ	✕
48: FastQC on data 14: RawData	ⓧ	✕
47: FastQC on data 14: Webpage	ⓧ	✕
46: FastQC on data 13: RawData	ⓧ	✕
45: FastQC on data 13: Webpage	ⓧ	✕
44: FastQC on data 12: RawData	ⓧ	✕
43: FastQC on data 12: Webpage	ⓧ	✕
42: FastQC on data 11: RawData	ⓧ	✕
41: FastQC on data 11: Webpage	ⓧ	✕

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Check the impact on the number of reads at each stage of the Pre Process, depending on the parameters selected. The parameter values depend on the target and the quality of the run. For example, the mismatch rate (the maximum rate of mismatches in the R1& R2 overlap region) depends directly on the quality of the run: the closer it is to 0, the less error is tolerated between the R1 and R2 sequences.

Step 4: FROGS Clustering swarm

Set the filtered dereplicated.fasta files and the count.tsv files from the previous Pre-processing step, as well as the aggregation distance (usually between 1 and 3), in order to cluster the sequences and execute the clustering statistics process.

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Galaxy France

Tools

Phylogenetics

Phenotype Association

GENOMICS TOOLKITS

Picard

deepTools

Homer

Giant

Gemini

EMBOSS

Searching tools

RAD-seq

Trinity

METAGENOMICS

Metagenomic Analysis

DADA2

FROGS

FROGS Demultiplex reads, attribute reads to samples in function of inner barcode

FROGS Pre-process: merging, denoising and dereplication

FROGS Clustering swarm: Single-linkage clustering on sequences

FROGS Remove chimera: Remove PCR chimeras in each sample

FROGS OTU Filters: Filters OTUs on several criteria

FROGS H5a: Extract the highly variable ITS1 and ITS2 subregions from ITS sequences

FROGS Affiliation OTU: Taxonomic affiliation of each OTU's seed by ID3tools and BLAST

FROGS Clustering swarm: Single-linkage clustering on sequences (Galaxy Version 4.0.1-galaxy1)

Sequences file

66: FROGS Pre-process: dereplicated.fasta

The dereplicated sequences file (format: FASTQ)

Count file

67: FROGS Pre-process: count.txt

It contains the count by sample for each sequence (format: TSV)

FROGS guidelines version

First guidelines until 3.1

The denoising step before a d3 clustering is no longer recommended since FROGS 3.2, but you can still choose it.

Aggregation distance clustering

Maximum number of differences between sequences in each aggregation swarm (step [d]-distance)

Efficient denoising? (equals to a first clustering step with d=1)

Yes

Clustering will be performed in two steps, first with distance = 1 and then with an aggregation distance of read input parameter (default: 1e) (d=denoising)

No

Send an email notification when the job completes.

Execute

What it does

Single-linkage clustering on sequences.

Inputs/Outputs

Inputs

Sequences file

Dereplicated sequences file from all samples (format FASTQ) ; strictly identical sequence are represented only one time and the initial count per sample is kept in the tabular count file.

The sequence ID must be "sequenceID:count" with X equal to the total abundance among all samples.

It corresponds to one output of FROGS Pre-process tools.

Count file

History

Rechercher des données

TSS1-GI-rdrp

66: report

790.39 MB

66: FROGS Pre-process: report.html

67: FROGS Pre-process: count.txt

66: FROGS Pre-process: dereplicated.fasta

62: MultiQC on data 60, data 58, and others: Webpage

61: MultiQC on data 60, data 58, and others: Stats

61: data 58, 3: Stats

60: FastQC on data 20: RawData

59: FastQC on data 20: Webpage

58: FastQC on data 19: RawData

57: FastQC on data 19: Webpage

56: FastQC on data 18: RawData

55: FastQC on data 18: Webpage

54: FastQC on data 17: RawData

53: FastQC on data 17: Webpage

52: FastQC on data 16: RawData

51: FastQC on data 16: Webpage

50: FastQC on data 15: RawData

49: FastQC on data 15: Webpage

48: FastQC on data 14: RawData

47: FastQC on data 14: Webpage

46: FastQC on data 13: RawData

45: FastQC on data 13: Webpage

44: FastQC on data 12: RawData

Check the clustering step by evaluating the number of clusters considering the total numbers of sequences.

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Step 5: FROGS Remove Chimera

Set input: seed_sequences.fasta and swarms_composition.tsv files from the previous clustering step and execute the tool.

Check the report, the proportion of clusters removed must not affect the proportion of abundance.

Step 6: FROGS OTU filter

Set the input files to the filtered 'remove_chimera.fasta' files and 'abundance.biom' files from the previous step.

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Usually, the minimum proportion parameter represented by an ASV is the one used. After running the tool, a report displays the number of ASVs selected with the filter and the share of abundance they represent.

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A final step converts the .biom file into a .fasta file containing the ASV sequences and an associated .tsv file containing the abundances corresponding to the filtered ASVs.

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Abundance file

The screenshot shows the Galaxy Datarmor interface. The main panel displays a workflow with two jobs. The first job is '23: FROGS BIOM to TSV: abundance.tsv', which is circled in red. The job details show the command used to generate the file: `Command: /app/bioinfo/frogs/2.0/app/biom_to_tsv.py --input-biom /home/datawork-bioinfo-ss/galaxy-prod/files/000/334/dataset_334302.dat --input-fasta /home/datawork-bioinfo-ss/galaxy-prod/files/000/334/dataset_334302.dat`. The 'History' panel shows a list of jobs, including '23: FROGS BIOM to TSV: abundance.tsv', '24: FROGS Clusters stat: summary.html', '22: FROGS Remove chimera: non_chimera_abundance.biom', '23: FROGS Filters: report.html', '23: FROGS Filters: excluded.tsv', '23: FROGS Filters: abundance.biom', '22: FROGS Remove chimera: report.html', and '22: FROGS Remove chimera: non_chimera_abundance.biom'.

Fasta file

The screenshot shows the Galaxy Datarmor interface. The main panel displays a workflow with two jobs. The first job is '23: FROGS Filters: abundance.biom', which is circled in red. The job details show the command used to generate the file: `Command: /app/bioinfo/frogs/2.0/app/filters.py --nb-cpus 28 --input-biom /home/datawork-bioinfo-ss/galaxy-prod/files/000/334/dataset_334299.dat --input-fasta /home/datawork-bioinfo-ss/galaxy-prod/files/000/334/dataset_334302.dat`. The 'History' panel shows a list of jobs, including '23: FROGS Filters: abundance.biom', '23: FROGS Filters: report.html', '23: FROGS Filters: excluded.tsv', '22: FROGS Remove chimera: report.html', and '22: FROGS Remove chimera: non_chimera_abundance.biom'.

Step 7: Taxonomic assignment

For taxonomic assignment of ASV sequences, we recommend using the online Norovirus Typing Tool Version 2.0" created by RIVM and detailed in Step 8 in Appendix B - Method 2 (EURL).

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Appendix B – Method 2 (EURL)

1. Introduction

Norovirus is one of the most common foodborne pathogens worldwide and causes frequent outbreaks of winter vomiting disease in Europe and the rest of the world. The virus occurs in several different genogroups, with genogroups I and II primarily infecting humans. In each genogroup there are many different genotypes of norovirus. In cases where a food has been contaminated with norovirus, via e.g., sewage pollution, several different genotypes may be present in the food. In an outbreak investigation, it is of great value to be able to link the virus found on a food with that found in the patient, to be able to trace the source of the contamination.

The genotypes of norovirus present in a contaminated food can be determined by sequencing part of the coding region for the virus capsid, so-called capsid typing.

Next Generation Sequencing (NGS) is a sequencing technique used to determine the order of nucleotides in entire genomes or selected genome regions. The technique sequences each copy of the virus genome region in parallel and generates large amounts of data. This enables all different genotypes in a sample to be identified simultaneously, unlike Sanger sequencing which can only identify the most abundant genotype.

2. Method reference

The method is developed in-house and is based on a previously unpublished Sanger method from the Swedish Public Health Agency. The development has been based on Illumina's protocol for the "16S Metagenomic Sequencing Library" (1, Part # 15044223 Rev. B) for the sequencing process and on the instruction "Amplicon Metagenomics Tutorial" (2, <https://www.geneious.com/tutorials/metagenomic-analysis/>) for the bioinformatics in the Geneious Prime software. Similar methods have also been evaluated by EFSA and are reported in "Application of Next Generation Sequencing on Norovirus contaminated oyster samples" (3, doi:10.2903/sp.efsa.2022.EN-7348).

3. Principle

This method is used after norovirus has been detected in a sample using RT-qPCR after virus extraction and nucleic acid purification. The different norovirus genogroups (I and II) are handled in parallel lines, but according to the same principle.

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Based on the RNA of the virus, cDNA is generated using specific primers complementary to part of the capsid gene, followed by amplification (one-step RT-PCR). After the initial RT-PCR, a second, semi-nested PCR is performed, where only the forward primers are replaced with new internal primers, amplifying a shorter PCR product. In addition, all primers used in the semi-nested PCR are modified at the 5' end with an Illumina-specific adapter sequence adapted for library preparation and sequencing on Illumina's NGS platform, so-called amplicon sequencing. After the PCRs, library preparation begins, where the PCR products are purified from primers and genomic material before being tagged with address sequences to be distinguished in the sequencing instrument. After another wash, a quality control step where the samples are analysed on a Bioanalyzer, will tell the size and concentration of the libraries. A sample library is created by normalizing and pooling the samples before loading them onto the sequencing instrument.

After the sequencing run is complete, a control is made of the obtained data, to ensure that it is of sufficient quality. The sequencing results, in the form of FASTQ files, are then processed through a pipeline in the Geneious Prime software. The sequences are trimmed and sorted out regarding length and quality. Then they are paired and assembled into several contigs. These contigs are genotyped with the "Norovirus genotyping tool" to determine which genotypes are present in the analysed sample.

4. Safety regulations

Illumina sequencing

When denaturing libraries for sequencing, sodium hydroxide (NaOH) is used. NaOH causes serious corrosive damage to the skin and eyes. Wear protective gloves and goggles during the denaturation step.

Well No. 8 in the reagent cassette contains formamide (denaturation buffer). Formamide is suspected of causing cancer, harming fertility, and harming the unborn child if exposed. Wear protective gloves when handling the reagent cartridge and waste bottle after completing the MiSeq run. The waste bottle is emptied in a fume hood into a waste container.

5. Instructions

Reagents

Table 1. Reagents.

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Reagent	Storage	Durability	Reference/Article no
Invitrogen SuperScript™ IV One-Step RT-PCR System	-20°C	According to the manufacturer	ThermoFisher/12594100
Invitrogen Platinum™ SuperFi™ II PCR Master Mix	-20°C	According to the manufacturer	ThermoFisher/12368010
RNAse-free/ultrapure water	2 to 8°C		
Agilent High Sensitivity DNA Kit (reagent + chip)	RT/2 to 8°C	According to the manufacturer	Agilent/5067-4626
10 mM Tris pH 8.5	-15 to -25°C		
AMPure XP beads	2 to 8°C	According to the manufacturer	Beckman Coulter/A63881
Day-fresh 80% ethanol	RT	12 h	
KAPA HiFi HotStart ReadyMix PCR Kit	-15 to -25°C	According to the manufacturer	Roche/KK2612
Nextera XT Index kit v2, Set AD	-15 to -25°C	According to the manufacturer	Illumina/FC-131-2001 to -2004
0.2 N NaOH	2 to 8°C	Maximum one week	Sigma-Aldrich/72068-100ML (10 M in H ₂ O)
HT1 Hybridization buffer	-15 to -25°C	According to the manufacturer	Illumina/20015892
MiSeq Reagent Nano Kit v2 (500 Cycles)	2 to 8°C/-15 to -25°C	According to the manufacturer	Illumina/MS-103-1003

Material

Pipettes and tips 1000 µl, 200 µl, 100 µl and 10 µl

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1.5 ml tube

Twin.tec PCR Plate 96, semi-skirted, green, Eppendorf, 0030 128. 591

Microseal 'B' film, BioRad, MSB1001

TruSeq Index Plate Fixture, Illumina, FC-130-1005

Apparatus

T100 Thermal Cycler, BioRad

Microcentrifuge, MiniSpin plus, Eppendorf

2100 Bioanalyzer Instrument (including chip priming station and vortex), Agilent

Eppendorf ThermoMixer and 1.5 ml block, Eppendorf

MiSeq instrument, Illumina

Software

Geneious Prime, Biomatters Ltd

Sequencing Analysis Viewer, Illumina

Controls

Table 2. Controls.

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Control	In this method	Storage	Durability	Reference
Negative Extraction Control (NEC)	If present from previous ISO-15216 extraction	RT/2 to 8°C		
Negative PCR control (NTC)	MQ/Ultrapure water	RT/2 to 8°C		
Internal Sequencing Control, PhiX Control Kit v3	20% in finished sequencing library	-15 to -25°C	According to the manufacturer	Illumina/FC-110-3001

Negative Extraction Control (NEC)

If there is a NEC previous used in an ISO-15215 analysis this control can be used as a negative control in this analysis. This would give a comprehensive control sample of the whole analysis.

Negative PCR control (NTC)

Nuclease-free water is added to a PCR well to control for non-specific signals and possible contamination in used reagents.

Internal Sequencing Control (PhiX)

The PhiX control comes from the small, well-characterized bacteriophage genome PhiX, and is an Illumina library with an average size of 500 bp and with a balanced base composition of ~45% GC and ~55% AT. Each pooled sequencing library must be diluted with 20% PhiX to reduce homogeneity. PhiX also serves as an internal check on the overall performance of the sequencing.

Analysis part 1 – generation of sequencing data

Step 1: PCR I

For primer sequences see table 3, for master mix see table 4 and for PCR program see table 5.

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The analysis for norovirus GI and GII takes place separately in separate PCR wells, but with the same PCR conditions. Unless otherwise stated, the samples, NTC and NEC are analysed with one replicate each. The PCR amplification is done on a thermal cycler instrument.

Table 3. PCR primers.

Primer Norovirus GI	Sequence 5'- 3'	Reference
GI_Fy (F)	GATTGTGGACAGGAGAYCGC	Unpublished (Public Health Agency of Sweden)
GI_CH (R)	CATGTTGCCAACCCAACCRTRTACA	Persson <i>et al.</i> , 2022
Primer Norovirus GII	Sequence 5'- 3'	Reference
GII_QNIF2D (F)	ATGTTACAGRTGGATGAGRTTCTCWGA	Loisy <i>et al.</i> , 2000
GII_CH (R)	ATACCACCAGCATRHCCRTRTAC	Unpublished, Swedish Food Agency

Table 4. PCR master mix.

Reagent	Amount per reaction (µl)	Final concentration
2X Platinum™ SuperFi™ RT-PCR Master Mix	12.5	1x
SuperScript™ IV RT Mix	0.25	
F primer (20 µM)	0.625	500 nM
R primer (20 µM)	1.125	900 nM
Nuclease-free water	5.5	
Template	5	

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Final volume	25
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Table 5. PCR program.

Step	Cycling	Temperature (°C)	Time
Annealing	1x	40	10 min
RT	1x	45	20 min
Preheating	1x	98	2 min
Denaturation		98	10 sec
Annealing	40x	50	30 sec
Extension/elongation		72	30 min
Final elongation	1x	72	5 min
Cooling	1x	4	∞

Step 2: PCR II

PCR II is a semi-nested PCR and should be handled as a post PCR analysis accordingly.

For primer sequences see table 6, for master mix see table 7 and for PCR program see table 8.

The primers are modified with Illumina's adapter sequences (underlined sequence in Table 3), so that obtained PCR products can be prepared for sequencing on Illumina's NGS platform.

The analysis for norovirus GI and GII takes place separately in separate PCR wells, but with the same PCR conditions. 5 µl product from PCR I is used as a sample in PCR II. Unless otherwise stated, the samples, NTC and NEC are spiked with one replicate each. No new NTC is needed for this PCR but the NTC from PCR I is used throughout the method. The PCR amplification is done on a Thermal Cycler instrument.

Table 6. PCR primers.

Primer	Sequence 5'- 3'	Reference
Norovirus GI		
GI_Fi AD (F)	<u>TCGTCGGCAGCGTCAGATGTGTATAAGAGACAGG</u> TAAATGATGATGGCGTCTA AG	Unpublished (Public Health Agency of Sweden)

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European Union Reference Laboratory
Foodborne Viruses

EURL Lm
European Union Reference Laboratory for
Listeria monocytogenes
<http://eur-lex.europa.eu>

GI_CH AD (R) GTCTCGTGGGCTCGGAGATGTGTATAAGAGACAGCATGTTGCCAACCAACCRT
TRTACA Persson *et al.*,
2022

Primer	Sequence 5'-3'	Reference
Norovirus GII		
GIISKF AD (F)	<u>TCGTCGGCAGCGTCAGATGTGTATAAGAGACAG</u> CNTGGGAGGGCGATCGCAA	Kojima <i>et al.</i> , 2002
GII_CH AD (R)	<u>GTCTCGTGGGCTCGGAGATGTGTATAAGAGACAG</u> ATACCACCAGCATRHCCRTTRT AC	Unpublished Swedish Food Agency

Underlined sequence = Illumina adapter sequences

Table 7. PCR master mix.

Reagent	Amount per reaction (µl)	Final concentration
2X Platinum™ SuperFi™ II PCR Master Mix	12.5	1x
F primer (20 µM)	0.625	500 nM
R primer (20 µM)	0.625	500 nM
Nuclease-free water	6.25	
PCR I product (sample)	5	
Final volume	25	

Table 8. PCR program.

Step	Cycling	Temperature (°C)	Time
Preheating	1x	98	30 sec
Denaturation		98	10 sec
Annealing	40x	52	10 sec
Extension/elongation		72	20 sec
Final elongation	1x	72	5 min
Cooling	1x	4	∞

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Step 3: AMPure wash 1 (PCR Clean-Up 1)

This step purifies the PCR products by removing residual PCR primers, as well as any Primer dimers and other non-specific products. 25 µL of PCR sample is washed with a 0.8x bead to sample ratio and finally eluted in 27.5 µL.

1. Room temperature the AMPure XP beads
2. Mix day-fresh 80% EtOH, 400 µl per sample
3. If necessary, centrifuge the PCR plate for 1 min at 1000 × g at RT to collect the condensate. Then carefully remove the PCR film
4. Vortex the AMPure XP beads for 30 sec to mix them
5. Pipette 20 µl of AMPure XP beads to each well of 25 µl of sample in the PCR plate

ATTENTION! The AMPure beads are viscous:

- When pipetting, the pipette tip should not go too far into the bead solution
 - When the beads are added to the sample well, pipetting should be done slowly
6. Pipette the entire volume in each PCR well up and down 10 times to mix
 7. Incubate 5 min at RT
 8. Place the PCR plate on the magnet for 2 min, or until the supernatant has cleared
 9. Use a multipipette to remove and discard the supernatant
 10. Leave the PCR plate on the magnet and wash the beads with fresh 80% EtOH:
 - a. Add 200 µl of fresh, 80% EtOH to each well of sample
 - b. Incubate 30 sec
 - c. Remove and discard the supernatant
 11. Leave the PCR plate on the magnet and wash the beads a second time:

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- a. Add 200 µl of fresh, 80% EtOH to each well of sample
 - b. Incubate 30 sec
 - c. Remove and discard the supernatant
 - d. Remove the last traces of EtOH with a 10 µl pipette
12. Allow the bead pellet to air dry for 10 min with the PCR plate still on the magnet
 13. Remove the PCR plate from the magnet and add 27.5 µl of 10 mM Tris pH 8.5 to each sample well
 14. Pipette gently up and down 10 times and ensure that the bead pellet is completely dissolved
 15. Incubate at RT 2 min
 16. Place the PCR plate on the magnet for 2 min, or until the supernatant has cleared
 17. Carefully transfer 25 µl of supernatant from the PCR plate to a new 96-well plate, alternatively pipette

The purified PCR products can be stored at -15° to -25°C, before library preparation continues with the index PCR.

Step 4: Index PCR

This step adds dual indexes as well as Illumina's sequencing adapters (P5 and P7) to the PCR products. For master mix see table 9 and for PCR program see table 10.

Important! Note which index set (A-D) is used and which indexes are used for which samples, as this information will be needed when setting up the sequencing run!

1. Use the Index plate (see Figure 2) to arrange:
 - A: Nextera XT index 2 primers (white caps)
 - B: Nextera XT index 1 primers (orange caps)
 - C: The 96-well PCR plate
2. Mix master mix according to table 9
3. Add 35 µl of master mix to each PCR well

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4. Add 5 µl index 1 and 5 µl index 2 primers to each well. First index 2 primer is added to all wells with samples in row A, second in row B, etc. First index 1 primer is added to all wells with samples in column 1, second in column 2, etc.
5. Using a multipipette, transfer 5 µl of washed PCR product from the previous PCR plate (from Step 3, AMPure wash 1) to the index PCR plate
6. Pipette the mix into each well (total volume 50 µl) up and down 10 times to mix. Cover the plate with PCR film and centrifuge for 1 min at 1000 × g RT
7. Run PCR according to PCR program in Table 10

Figure 2. The index plate, TruSeq Index Plate Fixture

Table 9. Index PCR master mix.

Reagent	Amount per reaction (µl)	Final concentration
2x KAPA HiFi HotStart ReadyMix	25	1x
MQ water	10	
Volume	35	

Table 10. Index PCR program.

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Step	Cycling	Temperature (°C)	Time
Preheating	1x	95	5 minutes
Denaturation		98	20 sec
Annealing	8x	55	30 sec
Extension/elongation		72	30 sec
Final elongation	1x	72	5 minutes
Hold	1x	4	∞

Step 5: AMPure wash 2 (PCR Clean-Up 2)

This step purifies the finished library before quantification. The entire product from the Index PCR is washed with a 0.8x bead to sample ratio and finally eluted in 27.5 µL.

1. Room temperature the AMPure XP beads
2. Mix day-fresh 80% EtOH, 400 µl per sample
3. If necessary, centrifuge the PCR plate for 1 min at 280 × g at RT to collect the condensate. Then carefully remove the PCR film
4. Vortex the AMPure XP beads for 30 sec to mix them
5. Pipette 40 µl of AMPure XP beads to each well with 50 µl of sample in the PCR plate

ATTENTION! The AMPure beads are viscous:

- When pipetting, the pipette tip should not go too far into the bead solution
 - When the beads are added to the sample well, pipetting should be done slowly
6. Pipette the entire volume in each PCR well up and down 10 times to mix
 7. Incubate 5 min at RT
 8. Place the PCR plate on the magnet for 2 min, or until the supernatant has cleared
 9. Use a multipipette to remove and discard the supernatant
 10. Leave the PCR plate on the magnet and wash the beads with fresh 80% EtOH:

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- a. Add 200 μ l of fresh, 80% EtOH to each well of sample
 - b. Incubate 30 sec
 - c. Remove and discard the supernatant
11. Leave the PCR plate on the magnet and wash the beads a second time:
- a. Add 200 μ l of fresh, 80% EtOH to each well of sample
 - b. Incubate 30 sec
 - c. Remove and discard the supernatant
 - d. Remove the last traces of EtOH with a 10 μ l pipette
12. Allow the bead pellet to air dry for 10 min with the PCR plate still on the magnet
13. Remove the PCR plate from the magnet and add 27.5 μ l of 10 mM Tris pH 8.5 to each sample well
14. Pipette gently up and down 10 times and ensure that the bead pellet is completely dissolved
15. Incubate at RT 2 min
16. Place the PCR plate on the magnet for 2 min, or until the supernatant has cleared
17. Carefully transfer 25 μ l of supernatant from the PCR plate to a new 96-well plate, alternatively pipe

The purified libraries can be stored at -15° to -25°C until the next step.

Step 6: Evaluation, quantification and dilution of ready-made libraries

The finished libraries are analysed on an Agilent 2100 Bioanalyzer, or similar, instrument to verify size. In the Bioanalyzer results, the concentration of the libraries is also obtained in ng/ μ l.

Dilute all finished sample libraries and controls 1:50 in water and analyze 1 μ l with the High Sensitivity kit according to the Agilent Bioanalyzer instructions.

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Different noroviruses can vary slightly in length but should be about 470-490 bp for GI and 490-520 bp for GII. The concentration is by default calculated on the region between 200-1000 bp (the area between the two blue lines under the tab "Region Table"):

Figure 3. Region used for calculating the concentration under the tab "Region Table" tab.

ATTENTION! If the peak of the library "hits the ceiling", i.e. the intensity of the peak is too high, the sample must be further diluted and analyzed again.

Calculate the DNA concentration in nM, based on the library size in bp and concentration in ng/μl obtained from the Bioanalyzer results:

$$\frac{\text{Conc. (ng/}\mu\text{L)} \times 50}{660 \text{ g/mol} \times \text{Average Size (bp)}} \times 10^6 = \text{concentration in nM}$$

Dilute finished libraries with 10 mM Tris pH 8.5 to 4 nM. Pool 5 μl of the diluted GI and GII libraries with unique indexes into a final library pool ready for sequencing. Desired sequencing depth per library determines how many libraries that can be pooled into the final library pool. For an Illumina Nano flow

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cell the validation has shown that at least 16 samples can be pooled into a final library and still yield enough sequencing depth.

Figure 4. The finished library's construction.

Step 7: Denaturation of libraries for sequencing

Pooled library is denatured with NaOH, diluted with hybridization buffer (HT1) and denatured with heat prior to cluster generation and MiSeq sequencing. The denatured library must also be diluted with 20% PhiX to reduce the homogeneity and thereby increase the quality of the sequencing results.

1. Set a heating block for 1.5 ml tubes at 96°C
2. Mix to 0.2 N NaOH
3. Thaw HT1 buffer (supplied with the reagent cassette) and then place it on ice
4. Dilute PhiX to 4 nM by mixing:
 - 2 µl 10 nM PhiX
 - 3 µl 10 mM Tris pH 8.5
5. Mix the following volumes to denature pooled library:
 - 5 µl 4 nM library
 - 5 µl freshly diluted 0.2 N NaOH
6. Mix the following volumes to denature PhiX:
 - 5 µl 4 nM PhiX
 - 5 µl freshly diluted 0.2 N NaOH

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7. Vortex and spin down
8. Incubate 5 min at RT
9. Add 990 µl chilled HT1 buffer. Vortex and spin down.

The library and PhiX are now at a concentration of 20 pM in 1 mM NaOH and can be saved at -15° to -25°C for up to four weeks.

10. Dilute denatured library with chilled HT1 buffer to 6 pM, or other desired concentration, according to Table 11. Vortex and spin down

Table 11. Dilution schedule for denatured library.

Final concentration	5 pM	6 pM	7 pM	8 pM	10 pM
Denatured library	150 µl	180 µl	210 µl	240 µl	300 µl
Chilled HT1 buffer	450 µl	420 µl	390 µl	360 µl	300 µl

Table 12. Dilution schedule for denatured PhiX.

Final concentration	5 pM	6 pM	7 pM	8 pM	10 pM
Denatured PhiX	40 µl	48 µl	56 µl	64 µl	80 µl
Chilled HT1 buffer	120 µl	112 µl	104 µl	96 µl	80 µl

11. Dilute denatured PhiX to the same concentration as the library. Dilute with chilled HT1 buffer to a total volume of 160 µl according to Table 12. Vortex and spin down
12. Combine the following volumes of diluted, denatured library and diluted, denatured PhiX:
 - 480 µl library
 - 120 µl PhiX

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This results in a finished sequencing library containing 20% PhiX

13. Place the sequencing library on ice until the next step.

When it is time to load the library into the reagent cartridge, proceed as follows:

14. Incubate the sequencing library for 2 min at 96°C in a heating block
15. Invert the tube 1-2 times to mix and then place the tube on ice for 5 min
16. Pierce the foil covering the "Load Sample" well in the reagent cartridge with a 1 ml pipette tip. With a clean 1 ml pipette tip load the entire volume of sequencing library without delay into the well.

Step 8: MiSeq setup and sequencing

Make sure that the instrument has been washed since previous runs according to instructions.

Different Illumina kits can be used for norovirus capsid genotyping, but it must have a cycling capacity of 500-600 cycles. The most cost-effective, and therefore preferred, kit for genotyping only a few samples is the MiSeq Reagent Nano Kit v2 (500 Cycles).

A sequencing run with a 500 cycles MiSeq Reagent Nano Kit v2 takes about 28 hours in total. When sequencing is complete, the MiSeq instrument must be washed again.

The sequencing parameters shall be as follows:

- Read 1: 251 cycles
- Index 1: 8 cycles
- Index 2: 8 cycles
- Read 2: 251 cycles

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Figure 5. The steps of sequencing into Read 1, Index 1, Index 2 and Read 2

Step 9: Evaluation of the sequencing run

In order to approve the completed sequencing run and consider the obtained sequencing data to be of sufficiently high quality for further bioinformatic analysis, various specifications from the MiSeq instrument should be evaluated. If necessary, the finished run can be further evaluated in the "Sequencing Analysis Viewer" (SAV) software. This software can be installed from the Illumina website.

Cluster Density

Stated in number of clusters (K) per mm². An approved sequencing run, where a Nano-chip v2 has been used, should have a cluster density of between 500-1200 K/mm². This indicates that enough data has been obtained without the risk of over clustering.

Clusters Passing Filter

Indicates the proportion (in %) of identified clusters that passed the filtering process that removes the least reliable (unclear, low-quality, and weak) clusters from the image analysis results, and the percentage of clusters that passed the filter should be $\geq 75\%$.

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Q-Score

The Q-score is a calculated probability that a base has been determined correctly, where Q30 indicates a 99.9% certainty. The percentage of bases \geq Q30 is an average over the entire MiSeq run. For a MiSeq Reagent Nano Kit v2 (500 Cycles), > 75% of the bases should be higher than Q30 to be able to consider the obtained sequencing data to be of high enough quality.

Estimated Yield

Estimated Yield indicates the estimated amount of data obtained from the sequencing run. For a MiSeq Reagent Nano Kit v2, the amount of data obtained should be around 500 MB.

Analysis part 2 – bioinformatic processing of sequencing data

The sequencing results per reads from the quality-controlled and approved MiSeq run need to be processed bioinformatically in the Geneious Prime software, to generate a norovirus genotype. The bioinformatic processing is done using a workflow of processing steps in a predetermined order:

Step 1: Upload FASTQ files

The raw data of the sequencing run must be copied from the MiSeq instrument to import the FASTQ files to a new folder in the Geneious Prime software:

1. Create a new folder in Geneious Prime
2. Mark relevant FASTQ files on your storage solution and drag them over to the new folder in Geneious Prime, by dropping them in the field marked "Drop files here to import"
3. Select the following import settings to upload the files from Read 1 and Read 2 as paired reads for each sample:

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FASTQ Sequences Import

Read Technology: Illumina

Don't pair (Sequences are unpaired or require advanced pairing after import via *Sequence->Set Paired Reads*)

Pair Paired End (inward pointing) pairs of files with insert size 300

Reset to Defaults ? OK Cancel

Step 2: End trimming

At the 5' end of the sequences, our specific primers remain from the PCR and must be removed. The Illumina instrument itself removes all sequences coming from Illumina tags and indexes, but the primers must be removed manually. Since the length of the primers differs between F/R and genogroups, GI and GII are trimmed with different settings. The function can also trim specific sequences but is not done in this SOP.

This is done most easily with the "Trim Ends" function, which can be set to trim a specific number of nucleotides in the 5' end.

1. Highlight a sample and choose; Annotate & predict → Trim Ends
2. Select the settings "Remove new trimmed regions from sequences" and Trim 5' End.
3. Select the number of bp to trim
 - a. Norovirus GI: 26
 - b. Norovirus GII: 24
4. Press OK and save the trimmed sequences

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Step 3: Quality trimming

To remove parts or whole sequences with poor quality (Q-score), they are trimmed with the BBDuk tool. Although the instrument removes the Illumina specific adapter sequences, we make sure by using the BBDuk default settings for removal of these.

1. Highlight the sample file and select; Annotate and Predict → Trim with BBDuk
2. Keep the “Trim Adapters” as default and the “Trim adapters based on paired read overhangs”, as seen on picture below
3. Choose to trim Low Quality at both ends with a minimum quality of 30
4. Choose to discard all sequences shorter than 90 bp

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5. Press OK and the software will create a new file with the same name but with the extension (Trimmed)

Trim using BBDuk

BBDuk Adapter/Quality Trimming Version 38.84 by Brian Bushnell

Trim Adapters

Adapters: All Truseq, Nextera and PhiX adapters (158 sequences) Choose... ?

Trim: Right End

Kmer Length: 27

Maximum Substitutions: 1

Maximum Substitutions + INDELS: 0

Trim partial adapters from ends with kmer length: 4

Trim Low Quality

Trim: Both Ends

Minimum Quality: 30

Trim adapters based on paired read overhangs

Minimum Overlap: 24

Discard Short Reads

Minimum Length: 90 bp

More Options

OK Cancel

Step 4: Merge Reads

All sequences now consist of two parts that can be merged if there is an overlap.

1. Mark the newly created file with the extension (Trimmed)
2. Choose; Sequence → Merge paired reads

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3. Make sure the Merge Rate is set to normal and click OK

Two new files will be created by this tool where one will have the location (Couldn't be merged) and the other (Merged) in the name. Here, the greater part of sequences should end up in the file (Merged) and the number has now been halved as two sequences have been combined into one.

Step 5: Extract Sequences

Since we are only interested in sequences of a certain length, these should be separated out.

1. Select the file with the extension (Merged)
2. In the results display box, select the "Lengths Graph" tab and click "Extract"
3. Set the max and min length of the sequences to be extracted (saved) with the settings: (The max setting can only be set as high as the length of the longest sequence occurring)
 - a. Norovirus GI: Min 260, Max 280
 - b. Norovirus GII: Min 290, Max 310

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The function creates a new file with the extension, "- length 290 to 310" (alternatively selected settings)

Step 6: Remove Chimeric reads

This method has not shown to generate a lot or any chimeric reads. To make sure, the UCHIME tool is integrated in Geneious but will take some time and needs a database of reference sequences to work. The databases used are constructed by using the reference sequences for both VP1 and RdRP, removing all duplicates, published in "Updated classification of norovirus genogroups and genotypes, Chhabra et al 2019".

The databases need to be copied to a folder in Geneious and kept in a list format. Keep the GI and GII lists separate.

1. Highlight the extracted sequences from the previous step
2. Select: Sequence → Remove Chimeric reads
3. Select a previously used database in the fold down "Reference Database" window or click Choose to link to a new database (listfile)

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4. Press OK

Remove Chimeric Reads

*UCHIME v4.2.40 Chimeric sequence detection using a reference database by Robert Edgar.
Note: de novo mode is not supported.*

Reference Database:

Include reverse complement

Save chimeric reads

Use USEARCH instead:

USEARCH is faster - get v8.1 from the author's [website](#)

Options

Minimum Reporting Score:

Weight of 'No' Vote:

Minimum Divergence Ratio: %

The function creates a new file with the extension, “(without chimeric reads)”. In the column “# Sequences” you can compare to the file before and see if any reads were removed.

Step 7: Cluster to Operational Taxonomic Units

Amplicon-based methods yield many sequences that are more or less the same. Typing each one individually would take a lot of time. Sequences that are very similar can be clustered to create a consensus sequence that can be typed instead. We call these clusters/consensus sequences Operational Taxonomic Units (OTUs).

To create OTUs, "De Novo assembly" is used with strict settings so that only the highly similar sequences are clustered.

1. Highlight the extracted sequences from the previous step
2. Select: Align/Assemble → De novo assembly
3. Enter settings according to the image below and click OK

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De Novo Assemble
✕

Data

Assemble by: 1st part of name, separated by -(Hyphen)

Assemble each sequence list separately Assemble each paired read separately

Use 100 % of data. Suitable for genome size between 0.1 MB and 0.5 MB.

Method

Assembler: Geneious

Sensitivity: Custom Sensitivity

Memory Required: Between 1.0 GB and 1.1 GB of 29 GB

Note: Paired reads can be set up or changed using Sequence > Set Paired Reads

Trim Before Assembly

Use existing trim regions

Remove existing trim regions from sequences

Trim sequences Options

Do not trim

Results

Assembly Name {Reads Name} Assembly

Save assembly report

Save list of unused reads

Save in sub-folder

Save contigs (Maximum 1,000)

Save consensus sequences Options

Advanced

Don't merge variants with coverage over approximately 6

Merge homopolymer variants

Circularize contigs of 3 or more sequences, if ends match

Produce scaffolds

Allow Gaps Maximum Per Read: 1 %

Maximum Gap Size: 1

Minimum Overlap: 250

Minimum Overlap Identity: 99 %

Word Length: 24

Index Word Length: 14

Ignore words repeated more than 200 times

Reanalyze threshold: 16

Maximum Mismatches Per Read: 1 %

Maximum Ambiguity: 4

Low Memory Use 1 2 3 4 5 Speed

Only use paired hits during assembly

Fewer Options ^
OK Cancel

The tool generates a new subfolder with the name of the sample. The folder contains the "contigs" that are created by alignment of the sequences. A contig contains at least two sequences, and sequences that are completely unique are collected in the "unused reads" file. It may vary how many contigs that are created, depending on whether there are several different genotypes in the same sample or

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whether the data may be of lower quality. A Consensus Sequences file is also obtained, that contains the consensus sequence from each contig.

Name ^	Description	Modified	% HQ	Sequence L...	# Sequences	% Pairwise L...	% Identical ...
Assembly Report	-	15 Apr 2024 1:02 pm	-	-	-	-	-
Consensus Sequences	-	15 Apr 2024 1:02 pm	-	-	4	-	-
Contig 1	21,021 reads from GI12_S10_L001_R_001 (trimmed) (merged) - length 290 to 300 assembled using Geneious	15 Apr 2024 1:02 pm	-	302	21,021	99.9%	3.7%
Contig 2	15 reads from GI12_S10_L001_R_001 (trimmed) (merged) - length 290 to 300 assembled using Geneious	15 Apr 2024 1:02 pm	100.0%	293	15	99.9%	99.0%
Contig 3	3 reads from GI12_S10_L001_R_001 (trimmed) (merged) - length 290 to 300 assembled using Geneious	15 Apr 2024 1:02 pm	100.0%	295	3	100.0%	100.0%
Contig 4	3 reads from GI12_S10_L001_R_001 (trimmed) (merged) - length 290 to 300 assembled using Geneious	15 Apr 2024 1:02 pm	100.0%	295	3	100.0%	100.0%
Unused Reads	-	15 Apr 2024 1:02 pm	-	-	13	-	-

To be able to use the result in the next step, it needs to be exported to a FASTA file.

1. Select the file "Consensus Sequences"
2. Choose File → Export → Documents
3. Rename the file to e.g., sample name+consensus sequences and make sure it is saved in a location where you can find it
4. Make sure Files of Type is set to *.fasta
5. Select export

Step 8: Typing of Operational Taxonomic Units

For genotyping, the online tool "Norovirus Typing Tool Version 2.0" created by RIVM is used. The tool can be found at:

<https://www.rivm.nl/mpf/typingtool/norovirus/>

1. Open the typing tool in a browser
2. Choose option B) to upload a FASTA file with sequences
3. Select the file you saved and make sure it uploads correctly.
4. Click the button "Start!" which will take you to a new results window.

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Norovirus Typing Tool Version 2.0

This tool is designed to use phylogenetic methods in order to identify the Norovirus genotype of a nucleotide sequence.
Note for batch analysis: The genotyping tool accepts up to 20000 sequences at a time.

The typing tool was updated to conform to the changes in the nomenclature.

[Updated classification of norovirus genogroups and genotypes, Chhabra P, de Graaf M, Parra GJ, Chan MC, Green K, Martella V, Wang Q, White PA, Katayama K, Vennema H, Koozmanns MPQ, Vinje J. J Gen Virol. 2019 Sep 4.](#)

New names are followed by old names in parenthesis on the results page and further described on the report page. New rare genotypes have been added, two genotypes have been assigned to new genogroups.

You may either:

- A. Paste one or more sequences in FASTA format in the input field.
- B. Upload a FASTA file.
- C. Upload FASTQ files.
- D. Revisit results of a previous run

A) Paste nucleotide sequence(s) in FASTA format:

Successfully uploaded file! Click Start to process the file.

B) Or, upload a FASTA with nucleotide sequences:

Norovirus Cons...Unpaired.fasta

C) Or, revisit results from a previous run:

Job-Id:

5. The process stops when all contigs are typed. The results are then downloaded.

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Norovirus Genotyping Tool Results

You may bookmark this page to revisit results of this job (65919585) later.

Name	Length	Family Genus Genogroup	BLAST score	polymerase	capsid	Report	genome
Contig	299	Caliciviridae Norovirus GII	79.93311		GII.2	Report	
Contig	293	Caliciviridae Norovirus GII	80.70176		GII.2	Report	
Contig	295	Caliciviridae Norovirus GII	79.2517		GII.17	Report	
Contig	295	Caliciviridae Norovirus GII	76.01476		GII.4 Sydney_2016	Report	

Download results: [XML File](#) [Table \(Excel format\)](#) [Table \(CSV format\)](#) [Sequences \(Fasta format\)](#)

6. Scroll to the bottom of the page and select "Download results: Table (Excel Format)", which will then be saved as an Excel file in your "Downloaded files" folder on your computer.
7. Each contig is presented on its own line and comes in the order it was exported from Geneious. If the number of original sequences of each contig is of interest, the number can be obtained from Geneious.

name	begin	length	end	BLAST	BLAST score	refseq	reverse complement	capsid type	capsid type support	capsid subtype	capsid subtype support
Contig	5068	299	5367	Caliciviridae Norovirus GII	79.93311	NC_029646	false	GII.2	100.0		
Contig	5071	293	5366	Caliciviridae Norovirus GII	80.70176	NC_029646	false	GII.2	100.0		
Contig	5071	295	5366	Caliciviridae Norovirus GII	79.2517	NC_029646	false	GII.17	100.0		
Contig	5071	295	5366	Caliciviridae Norovirus GII	76.01476	NC_029646	false	GII.4	100.0	Sydney_2016	99.0

References

Persson, S., Larsson, C., Simonsson, M. *et al.* *rprimer*: an R/bioconductor package for design of degenerate oligos for sequence variable viruses. *BMC Bioinformatics* **23**, 239 (2022).

<https://doi.org/10.1186/s12859-022-04781-0>

Chhabra P, de Graaf M, Parra GI, Chan MC, Green K, Martella V, Wang Q, White PA, Katayama K, Vennema H, Koopmans MPG, Vinjé J. Updated classification of norovirus genogroups and genotypes. *J*

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Gen Virol. 2019 Oct;100(10):1393-1406. doi: 10.1099/jgv.0.001318. Erratum in: J Gen Virol. 2020 Aug;101(8):893. doi: 10.1099/jgv.0.001475. PMID: 31483239; PMCID: PMC7011714.